

Unveiling Innovation Potential of Circular Approaches
in Automotive Electronics and Beyond

Eco-design Guidelines for Functional Electronics

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary	3
2	Introduction	4
2.1	EU regulatory framework	4
2.2	Key areas for material circularity of functional electronics	5
3	Environmental and circular product guidelines within the UNICORN project.....	7
3.1	Circular economy strategies	8
3.2	Renewable materials	9
3.2.1	Fossil- and bio-based polycarbonate	10
3.2.2	Bio-based polycarbonate and polyamide	13
3.2.3	Fossil- and bio-based PET.....	15
3.2.4	Discussion and Conclusion.....	16
3.3	Recycled materials	17
3.3.1	Virgin and recycled PET	18
3.3.2	Virgin and recycled Silver	21
3.3.3	Discussion and Conclusion.....	22
3.4	Use of different materials	23
3.4.1	Silver and copper.....	24
3.4.2	Silver and aluminium	25
3.4.3	Aluminium and copper	26
3.4.4	Conclusion.....	27
3.5	Critical raw materials	28
4	Conclusions & Perspectives	29
5	References.....	30
6	Annexes	33
6.1	Annex A: Life cycle inventories and additional background information	33
6.2	Annex B: The environmental impact categories of the Product Environmental Footprint methodology	40
6.3	Annex C: List of critical raw materials	42
6.4	Annex D: Eco-design requirements according to the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR).....	44

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Executive summary

This report provides guidelines for the identification, evaluation, and prioritisation of eco-design measures for functional electronics in smart components, with the aim of reducing their environmental impact and improving circularity. The guidance is based on life cycle assessment (LCA) of different eco-design options relevant to this project, complemented by further considerations and background information.

Assessments were performed from a cradle-to-gate perspective, covering raw material production, transport, and manufacturing. The analyses are based on data from the ecoinvent database and information obtained from the UNICORN project Use Cases (UCs). The emphasis is on guidance, underpinned by consolidated knowledge from scientific literature and practical experiences from the projects UCs. The analyses of the eco-design measures are decoupled from the specific and limiting contexts of the individual use cases. This approach enables the formulation of broader eco-design insights that extend beyond the project scope and support the development of general design principles for sustainable and circular electronics.

Material optimisation is identified as a key strategy, with recycled materials, second-generation feedstock, secondary metals, and minimisation of CRM use as essential design considerations. However, the report emphasises that a holistic approach is essential to account for potential trade-offs, not only between different environmental impacts, but also in terms of circularity and end-of-life performance. Furthermore, when applying these guidelines, it is important to take into consideration the specific production practices, usage conditions, and end-of-life scenarios relevant to the components under study, as these factors strongly influence the overall performance. The aim of this report is to provide an overview of important aspects that need to be considered together with a structure for assessing eco-design options.

Eco-design cannot be addressed solely at the component level. It must be embedded in the wider product and system architecture. In addition to material choices, strategies such as product lifetime extension, process optimisation, and reuse can further strengthen circularity potential. However, these measures are not elaborated in detail in this guidance as these are highly context-dependent and must be tailored to each specific system, as practices and system characteristics strongly influence their effectiveness. Nevertheless, in most cases the greatest benefits are achieved when such strategies are applied in combination rather than in isolation.

Overall, eco-design measures can play a decisive role in advancing the sustainability of functional electronics in smart systems. By prioritising secondary materials, second-generation feedstocks, and circular design principles, while fostering collaboration across the value chain, eco-design can leverage the contribution of functional electronics to the objectives of a circular and resource-efficient economy.

1 Introduction

This report presents a set of environmental and circular product design guidelines, developed within the context of the UNICORN project, with a specific focus on functional electronics integration in the automotive sector. These guidelines result from a systematic consolidation of the guidance provided to project partners throughout the UNICORN project and the practical insights gained from the application of eco-design principles across the various Use Cases (UCs).

The primary objective of these guidelines is to support electronics designers and developers in integrating environmental sustainability and circularity into their product design processes—both during the project and beyond its scope. They serve as a bridge between project-specific knowledge and general design practice, facilitating long-term impact.

The scope of this report includes:

- Transferring the informed guidance provided on material, component, and system levels of the UCs. The UCs are described in UNICORN deliverables D2.9-12, D3.9-12);
- Providing guidance on embedding environmental and circularity considerations into the early stages of design;
- Incorporating findings from sustainability assessments, with careful attention to trade-offs between environmental and circularity benefits (described in D4.2 (confidential deliverable) and functional performance, robustness, and reliability (assessed by technical UC partners in D2 and D3);
- Offering actionable, generalisable design principles to enable future users, particularly designers and developers of printed electronics, to apply circularity and sustainability in electronics design beyond the confines of this project, which focusses on functional electronics in the automotive sector.

There relevance of eco-design guidelines for functional electronics is underscored by the EU policy landscape concerning product eco-design and broader sustainability goals, and by existing literature highlighting eco-design opportunities for materials used in functional electronics and the systems in which they are implemented. Section 1.1 introduces the EU regulatory framework and section 1.2 discusses some opportunities for material circularity in functional electronics. Indeed, the primary focus of this report is on material selection, where D4.4 (Willot P. et al., 2025) focuses on the systems perspective and the net benefits that can be achieved by applying functional electronics in mobility system.

1.1 EU regulatory framework

In July 2024 the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR; 2024/1781) entered into force, replacing the Eco-design Directive (2009/125/EC). The ESPR serves as the foundation of the EU Commission's strategy for advancing to more environmentally sustainable and circular products. While the Eco-design Directive provided a framework for setting performance criteria specifically for energy-related products, focussing primarily on energy consumption, the ESPR broadens this scope to cover almost all physical products. This new regulation introduces a comprehensive eco-design framework, which provides the European Commission a framework to establish eco-design requirements across a wide range of product categories. These requirements encompass, on the one hand, performance criteria, (e.g. durability, resource efficiency) and, on the other hand, information transparency measures. A list of eco-design requirements according to the ESPR is given in annex D. The ESPR mandates transparency by means of the Digital Product Passport (DPP), ensuring that essential sustainability information is readily accessible.

Under the Eco-design Directive the Eco-design and Energy Labelling Work Plan (EDELWP) for 2022 to 2024 covered 35 product groups targeted for new or revised eco-design and energy labelling regulations. Under the ESPR a new work plan was established and according to article 79(1)(a)(i) of the ESPR, 19 listed products fall under the transitional regime with a view to adopt relevant measures pursuant to the Eco-design Directive until the end of 2026.

The regulation is a key component of a broader set of measures aimed at fulfilling the goals outlined in the 2020 Circular Economy Action Plan, which serves as a fundamental pillar of the European Green Deal. The EU Green Deal (2019) aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, with a strong focus on waste prevention, material recovery, and product circularity.

Other key regulations relevant to the automotive and electronics sectors include the REACH Regulation and the RoHS Directive (2015/863/EU)^a. REACH aims to protect human health and the environment from the harmful effects of chemical substances, while RoHS restricts hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment (EEE). In parallel, the WEEE Directive promotes the collection, recycling, and responsible disposal of electronic waste.

In a similar vein, the End-of-Life Vehicles (ELV) Directive lays down rules to ameliorate the circularity of the automotive sector, ensuring resource efficiency and environmental protection with measures such as recycling targets and use of recycled plastics in new vehicles. The Batteries Regulation sets sustainability and circularity requirements to minimise the impact of batteries throughout their entire life cycle.

These regulations and directives play an important role in advancing the Green Deal sustainability goals. Many of these policies have been recently updated, or are in the process of being revised, to further align with the Green Deal's circular economy and environmental goals.

1.2 Key areas for material circularity of functional electronics

Approximately two-thirds of GHG emissions are linked to material use. Emissions from material use alone are expected to increase from 30 Gt CO₂-eq in 2017 to 50 Gt CO₂-eq in 2060 while primary materials use is projected to double in the next decades (from 79 Gt in 2011 to 167 Gt 2060). (OECD, 2019)

Over the past years, the search for more sustainable, alternative plastic materials has become an important trend, aiming to reduce the environmental and climate impacts of fossil-based plastics. Bio-based plastics (bioplastics) are often regarded as the go-to materials to replace fossil-based plastics in order to reduce the environmental burdens, mainly associated with the extraction of petrochemical input materials. However, as can be derived from **Figure 1**, biomass production is associated with environmental burdens as well. Therefore, it is crucial that these bio-based plastics are produced sustainably, utilising efficiently sourced raw materials and, preferably, second-generation feedstock such as biological waste streams, or by-products. (Deckers J. et al., 2023).

The use of recycled materials is key in respect to reducing the need for virgin materials and the mitigation of waste generation and the related environmental burdens. Nevertheless, it should be kept in mind that the most important approach to minimise the impacts of waste is to reduce, or whenever possible, avoid unnecessary use of materials in general.

Figure 1 shows that even though metals, for example, only take up a small fraction in terms of their mass, their environmental footprint is large.

^a The RoHS Directive currently restricts the use of ten substances: lead, cadmium, mercury, hexavalent chromium, polybrominated biphenyls (PBB) and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE), bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), butyl benzyl phthalate (BBP), dibutyl phthalate (DBP) and diisobutyl phthalate (DIBP).

Figure 1: Amount (left) and environmental footprint (right) of materials consumed in the EU-27, 2019 (European Environmental Agency, 2023)

The production of primary (virgin) metals generally involves a sequence of steps: ore mining and concentration, followed by smelting or separation, and finally refining to obtain the element in its metallic form. Multiple processing routes are possible, depending on the ore type and desired product. At each stage, impurities and by-products are removed, and the concentration of the target metal in the material stream increases. Achieving the required purities during the refining stage often entails energy-intensive, precisely controlled melting operations, which frequently rely on fossil fuels, either directly as a reductant or indirectly, to supply heat and electricity. (Nuss and Eckelman, 2014) Moreover, the anticipated growth in the use of metals brings along additional environmental impacts beyond greenhouse gas emissions. The extraction and use of metals significantly contribute to toxicity and ecosystem degradation.

Increasing the use of secondary materials can significantly reduce environmental impacts. As shown the CO₂-impact of secondary materials is estimated to be considerably lower than that of their primary counterparts.

Because many metals are considered critical according to the European Commission’s criticality assessment (Grohol M. and Veeh C., 2023), it is crucial that they are used in a sustainable and efficient manner. Effectively organising material cycles is therefore essential for example, by ensuring the sustainable use of the available metal stock.

This stock includes not only the extractable reserves found in mines but also the metals embedded in the so-called urban mine. The urban mine refers to the valuable materials contained in end-of-life products such as electronic devices, vehicles, and other equipment resources that are, to a certain extent, recoverable.

* Global average over all pathways used to recycle zinc in 2020

Figure 2: CO₂-impact savings of secondary production compared to primary production (%). (Gregoir L., 2022)

2 Environmental and circular product guidelines within the UNICORN project

This section provides an overview of the guidance provided throughout the UNICORN project, for the different use cases. The eco-design measures are not strictly tied to individual use cases but are instead presented agnostically, as standalone strategies or best practices. Their technical feasibility is ensured, as they originate from use case partners and reflect realistic alternative materials, processes, or design strategies. While these measures are applicable within the systems studied in the UCs, confidentiality constraints prevent direct linkage to specific products or partners. The analyses of the eco-design measures are decoupled from the specific and limiting contexts of the individual use cases. This approach enables the formulation of broader eco-design insights that extend beyond the project scope and support the development of general design principles for sustainable and circular electronics.

The guidelines are aligned with existing EU regulatory frameworks, such as the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), the Eco-design Directive, REACH, RoHS and the End-of-Life Vehicles Directive.

The guidelines are informed by insights gained from the UCs within the UNICORN project. As can be derived from **Table 1** most design improvements identified within the UCs, focused primarily on alternative material selection as the main eco-design strategy. Material substitutions are grouped in changes to material origin (renewable and recycled) or changing to a different material. In addition to alternative material selection, this report briefly introduces broader circular economy strategies relevant to functional electronics, as part of a wider discussion on circular design principles (see section 2.1).

Table 1: Eco-design principles and guidance for material circularity in functional electronics design discussed in this report

Eco-design principle	Section
Environmental performance of renewable materials: Fossil- and bio-based polycarbonate Bio-based polycarbonate and polyamide Fossil- and bio-based Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET)	2.2
Environmental performance of recycled materials: Virgin and recycled PET Virgin and recycled Silver	2.3
Environmental performance of different materials: Silver and Copper Silver and Aluminium Aluminium and Copper	2.4
Critical raw materials	2.5

The environmental impacts of the electronics are calculated and assessed using commonly accepted LCA-methodology. For performing the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) and generating the environmental profiles the LCA software package “SimaPro 9.1.1” is used. Different methods for impact assessment exist, which are recognised by experts worldwide. This study uses the impact categories and characterisation factors of the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method (Andreasi et al., 2023) developed by the European Commission in the framework of the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF). An overview of the EF impact categories is provided in **Annex B (5.2)**.

PEF also proposes a single score, which is an aggregated measure that combines multiple environmental impact categories into a single, dimensionless value, expressed in Pt (points). This value is obtained through normalisation and weighting. Normalisation depicts the results of the different environmental impact categories into a common scale, enabling comparison and allowing aggregation by means of a weighting step. The reference values, or normalisation

factors, represent the total impact of a reference activity in a reference region for a certain impact category (e.g. climate change, eutrophication, etc.) in a reference year (Sala, S. et al., 2017). However, it must be noted that the inventory coverage and robustness for some impact categories are low. This can distort the results and lead to an overestimation of the importance of the impact category for a product group.

In the weighting step, indicator results are aggregated across impact categories using numerical factors based on value-choices. The resulting weighted scores are summed to obtain a single impact score (Sala, S. et al., 2018). The EF method uses standardised weighting factors developed by the European Commission (European Commission, 2021). However, as pointed out by the authors (Sala, S. et al., 2018) weighting factors are not mainly natural science based but inherently involve value choices that will depend on policy, cultural and other preferences and value systems. No “consensus” on weighting seems to be achievable. This situation does not apply only to weighting in a LCA or EF context but seems inevitable for many multicriteria approaches. However, weighting is seen as essential to further aggregate information with the objective to provide better support in complex decision situations (Sala, S. et al., 2018).

When interpreting these results, it is important to note the limitations of the normalisation factors and the fact that weighting factors are subject to choices.

The results are calculated from a cradle-to-gate perspective, accounting for raw materials production, transportation of raw materials and manufacturing processes of intermediate materials. Subsequent life cycle stages are not included in the analysis. However, when relevant, the potential implications of switching to a different material on later life cycle stages, such as end-of-life, are discussed qualitatively.

Additionally, the following aspects must be kept in mind for all LCA results:

- The use of *capital goods and infrastructure* are included in the environmental assessment for all processes (production of basic materials, additives, energy, transport etc.). For example, the impact of the pipelines for natural gas is considered, as well as the impact of the production of transport modes (e.g. trucks) and transport infrastructure (e.g. roads).
- *Accidental pollutions* are often difficult to distinguish from emissions that occur under normal conditions (accidental pollutions are not measured and reported separately) and are therefore not considered in the environmental impact assessment.
- Not explicitly addressed are social and other work environment aspects including workplace-exposure, and indoor-emissions. These are impacts that occur directly within the technosphere (e.g. workplace exposure) and are not normally covered by attributional LCA.
- Environmental impacts caused by the *personnel of production plants* are neglected, e.g. waste from the cafeteria and sanitary installations, or environmental effects caused by commuter traffic.

2.1 Circular economy strategies

The circular economy aims to maximise resource utilisation and reduce waste by maintaining the value of products and materials in use for as long as possible. Central to this approach are the ‘R’ strategies, which are widely recognised as a framework for the transition to a circular economy. The ‘R’ strategies are summarised in **Figure 3**.

As highlighted in a recent report by the European Environment Agency (2024), while the EU has made some progress, the overall circularity rate remains low, at 11.5% as of 2022. This demonstrates that there is a significant need to accelerate the transition, which starts with reducing the demand for materials.

The principles of the circular economy R-strategies have great similarities to environmental mitigation actions. Overall, reducing the materials demand, will reduce the environmental impact. By prolonging product lifetime, the demand for new products and associated raw materials is reduced. Material reductions can also be achieved by design changes, such as reducing product weight or optimising dimensions to reduce scrap generation. A

straightforward principle is that reducing the quantity of a given material (both in the final product as in the format of industrial scrap) lowers its environmental impact, since fewer resources are extracted, processed, and disposed of.

Figure 3: 10 R-strategies of the circular economy (Malooly L. and Daphne T., 2023)

However, when circular strategies involve alternative materials (renewable, recycled, or different materials altogether) the environmental impact of these changes need to be properly investigated. Such substitutions can create environmental trade-offs, with some impact categories improving while others worsen. These results are discussed more detailed in the following sections.

2.2 Renewable materials

Within the UNICORN project, the replacement of petrochemical plastics with bio-based plastics is assessed.

Examples of these bio-based materials include bio-polyethylene terephthalate (bioPET), bio-polyethylene (bioPE), bio-based polyamide (bioPA), polylactic acid (PLA), bio-polycarbonate (bioPC), polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) and starch-based composites. Two types of bio-based plastics are the so-called ‘drop-in’ bio-based plastics that are structurally identical to their petrochemical counterparts (bioPE and bioPET) or the alternative bio-based polymers, such as PLA and PHA that exhibit different chemical structures and properties compared to conventional plastics.

This section offers guidance on the environmental implications of the use of petrochemical and bio-based materials. The following eco-design measures are assessed:

- (1) Use of conventional polycarbonate versus bio-based polycarbonate
- (2) Use of bio-based polycarbonate versus bio-based polyamide
- (3) Use of fossil-based PET versus bioPET

As emphasised by the ESPR, these renewable materials must be sustainable as well. To assess their environmental sustainability, the environmental impact of the production of 1 kg of the considered materials is analysed and presented. Most substrates examined in the

UNICORN case studies can be replaced one-to-one with their renewable counterpart, however, this may vary depending on the design context. If differences in material consumption arise, this should be taken into account when comparing alternative solutions. More detailed information on the life cycle inventories of the different materials is provided in **Annex A (5.1)**.

2.2.1 Fossil- and bio-based polycarbonate

Polycarbonate (PC) stands out as one of the most widely used engineering plastics, valued for its transparency, thermal stability, and mechanical strength. Consequently, the demand for PC is particularly high in rapidly advancing industries like the electric vehicle sector for which PC is instrumental in reducing weight, directly improving energy efficiency and driving range. Currently, bisphenol A-based polycarbonate (BPA-PC) dominates industrial production, relying on both phosgene-based and phosgene-free synthesis routes that are both considered in the scope of this report. (Zhou et al., 2023)

Conventional polycarbonate synthesis pathways

Option 1: BPA + Phosgene (COCl_2) → Polycarbonate

Option 2: BPA + diphenyl carbonate (DPC) → Polycarbonate

Bio-based polycarbonate synthesis pathways

Option 3: Isosorbide + Phosgene (COCl_2) → Bio-based polycarbonate

Option 4: Isosorbide + DPC → Bio-based polycarbonate

The synthesis routes presented above were chosen because they reflect both the dominant industrial practices for conventional PC production and the most relevant emerging alternatives for bio-based PC.

2.2.1.1 Fossil-based polycarbonate

In the conventional synthesis process bisphenol A (BPA) and phosgene are polymerised into PC. However, the use of BPA raises concerns as it is classified as a hazardous chemical in the EU (ECHA, 2017; (EEA, 2023). The second building block, phosgene, is a highly toxic gas (Occupational Safety and Health Administration). Phosgene is synthesised through the reaction of carbon monoxide (CO) and chlorine gas (Cl_2) in the presence of activated carbon catalyst (Dobovetzky et al., 1978). Due to its extreme toxicity, phosgene is typically produced and consumed on-site in closed systems to minimise exposure risk. (Bast and Glass-Mattie, 2015)

The phosgene-based PC production process has drawbacks such as environmental burdens and safety problems associated with this highly toxic reagent. Furthermore, its use results in the formation of chlorine salts, and large amounts of methylene chloride. Therefore, diphenyl carbonate (DPC) is often considered as a substitution for phosgene to synthesise polycarbonate resins. (Gong et al., 2007) Generally, the non-phosgene melt transesterification route utilises diphenyl carbonate (DPC) and diols as reactants, while DPC can be synthesised by transesterification from phenol and dimethyl carbonate (DMC) (Wang et al., 2023).

The phosgene-based route (option 1) remains the most widely used process at industrial scale due to its high efficiency, while the DPC route (option 2) offers a phosgene-free alternative that is gaining traction due to improved safety and environmental considerations (Gong et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2023).

2.2.1.2 Bio-based polycarbonate

On the bio-based side, isosorbide has emerged as a promising renewable substitute for BPA, derived from glucose via sorbitol. The use of DPC with isosorbide (option 4) represents a main synthesis pathway explored at research and pilot scales for producing bio-based PC (bioPC).

For sake of completeness and comparison, the use of isosorbide in combination with phosgene (option 3) was also considered, however, this is a less common synthesis pathway.

The synthesis method for isosorbide bio-based PC is fundamentally consistent with conventional BPA-PC. In general, there are two synthesis routes that can be applied namely, step growth polycondensation and ring opening polymerisation. To closely align with the classical phosgene-based synthesis pathway, characterised by step-growth polycondensation, isosorbide is considered as a bio-based building block for bioPC production. This compound undergoes melt transesterification which is a typical step growth polycondensation reaction as well.

In the synthesis process of bio-based polycarbonate (BioPC), bisphenol A (BPA) is replaced by a biomass-derived compound, in this case isosorbide but this can also be another bio-based diol. These renewable compounds are derived from plant materials such as glucose, cellulose, or starch, making the polycarbonate partially or fully bio-based, depending on the specific process and composition. Typically, isosorbide is derived from glucose through catalytic processes. Isosorbide has a structure similar to BPA, allowing it to participate in polymerisation to form the polycarbonate. Nevertheless, isosorbide is generally considered to be safer and is not an endocrine disruptor. The core chemical reaction involves the polycondensation of isosorbide (or another bio-based compound) with phosgene or an alternative reagent (such as DPC) to produce the polymer backbone of polycarbonate. The bio-based feedstock considered for bio-PC production in this assessment is maize.

2.2.1.3 The environmental performance of conventional and bio-based polycarbonate

The environmental performance of conventional fossil-based polycarbonate (PC) and bio-based polycarbonate (bioPC) assessed within the UNICORN project is shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 presents the environmental performance of conventional and bio-based polycarbonate synthesis routes. The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile of the four synthesis pathways across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors (e.g. BPA, phosgene, isosorbide, or DPC) are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. solvent, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey.

Figure 4: Relative environmental performance of 1 kg fossil-based polycarbonate and 1 kg bio-based polycarbonate. The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile of the four synthesis pathways across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors (e.g. BPA, phosgene, isosorbide, or DPC) are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. solvent, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey.

The results indicate that shifting to bio-based feedstocks in combination with the shift to less toxic reagents has the potential to reduce environmental burdens. However, these impact savings are not uniform and largely depend on the impact category considered, together with the synthesis route and production practices.

The shift to the use of less toxic DPC instead of phosgene (for both fossil and bio-based PC) shows no improvement, to the contrary. There are two main reasons for this. Firstly, the higher impact of DPC is most likely attributable to the multi-step synthesis of diphenyl carbonate (DPC), which is more energy- and resource-intensive due to the use of fossil-derived intermediates, namely phenol and dimethyl carbonate (DMC). These intermediates are

required in the non-phosgene synthesis route, where DPC is used as a safer alternative to phosgene. As a result, the increased energy and resource intensity translates mainly into higher climate change related impacts and increased impacts in terms of fossil-based resource use. Consequently, even though the DPC route avoids the use of toxic phosgene, it often requires more energy and more raw materials for its production leading to a limited impact reduction when considering bio-based PC.

Secondly, it is important to highlight that phosgene's toxicity is mainly associated with occupational risks, which are not included in the LCA method. As mentioned in the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) handbook, the direct health effects, whether positive or negative, that products may have on humans are also not accounted for in LCA. This is because such impacts occur within the technosphere and are not mediated by environmental fate or exposure pathways, which are the basis for impact assessment in LCA. Similarly, impacts that arise directly within the technosphere, such as workplace exposure, are not explicitly addressed. In summary, aspects like occupational accidents, social conditions, work environment factors (including exposure at the workplace), and indoor emissions typically fall outside the scope of attributional LCA methods. (European Commission - Joint Research Centre, 2010). Additionally, the use of special closed-system infrastructure is required to handle toxic phosgene safely which can be associated with additional burdens.

The use of isosorbide from maize as bio-based feedstock is associated with some trade-offs as well, mainly in terms of impact categories such as eutrophication, land use and water use that are typically associated with agricultural practices. Consequently, the environmental performance of bio-based materials is strongly influenced by the agricultural practices associated with their cultivation. Hence, bio-based materials should be confirmed to be, preferably, obtained from regenerative agricultural practices and sustainably sourced. In fact, to avoid additional environmental burdens or shift in burdens, these should be ideally derived from by-products or waste streams.

2.2.2 Bio-based polycarbonate and polyamide

Polyamides (PA), commonly referred to as nylons, are a group of industrial polymers characterised by their repeating amide linkages. Nylons are synthesised by multiple synthetic routes, via polycondensation reactions of dicarboxylic acids with diamines, or by polycondensation of amino acids or via ring-opening polymerisation (ROP) of cyclic amides (lactams). (Farahat M., 2021)

In light of the increasing environmental concerns and climate change, growing attention is directed to advancing the chemical industry to carbon neutrality and reducing the environmental burdens in general. Therefore, bio-based polyamides are considered promising alternatives, being, at least partially, derived from renewable resources. More specifically, biopolyamides, such as PA4,10; PA5,10; PA6,10; PA10,10; and PA10,12 are considered partially bio-based when only one of the monomers, typically the dicarboxylic acid, originates from renewable resources. When both the diamine and dicarboxylic acid are bio-sourced, these materials are classified as fully bio-based and commonly derived from castor bean oil such as PA11. Plant oils and fats have been used for a long time as main biomass feedstocks for the synthesis of bioPAs. (Farahat M., 2021; Winnacker M. and Reiger B., 2016; Ogunsona et al., 2019)

Within the context of this project, PA11 was explored, together with bioPC, as alternative substrate material to fossil-based PC. This polyamide is synthesised via polycondensation of amino acids and therefore fully bio-based. The synthesis process starts with the extraction and refining of castor bean oil, the shells of the beans are removed followed by mechanical pressing to obtain triglycerides (oil). The subsequent saponification (or transesterification) step affords ricinoleic acid, the primary fatty acid component. Through pyrolytic cleavage, ricinoleic acid is converted into 10-undecenoic acid, a key intermediate for the production of 11-aminoundecanoic acid. The latter is obtained via bromination and subsequent amination. Finally, the obtained monomer undergoes polycondensation to form bio-based polyamide 11 (PA11, nylon 11). (Winnacker M. and Reiger B., 2016; Farahat M., 2021)

In this study, the bio-based PA11 synthesis route was approximated and evaluated in comparison with bioPC, using maize as bio-based feedstock, and conventional PC. Bio-based PA11 will hereafter be referred to as bioPA. A description of the life cycle inventory together with material input flows selected for the synthesis of bioPA are provided in **Annex A (5.1.3)**.

2.2.2.1 The environmental performance of bio-based polyamide and bio-based polycarbonate compared to fossil-based polycarbonate

The environmental performance of bio-based polyamide 11 (bioPA, PA11) in comparison to the environmental performance of bioPC (non-phosgene route) and fossil-based PC, both described in the previous section, was critically assessed.

In the considered data inventory, bromine is derived from brine, a process that requires the use of chlorine and heat from steam. These inputs mainly contribute to the environmental burdens of bromine, especially in terms of climate change and use of fossil-based resources. Similarly, acetic acid has the highest impacts related to climate change and fossil-based resource use, which mainly originates from the use of carbon monoxide for the carbonylation of methanol and methanol itself, which are both fossil-based.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the involvement of the bromination step in the synthesis of 11-aminoundecanoic acid from undecenoic acid largely depends on the specific PA synthesis route considered. Accordingly, the assumptions made regarding the synthesis pathway, combined with the high level of uncertainty in the approximation of the synthesis process, render the results insufficiently robust to be presented as a stand-alone figure without risking misinterpretation.

Preliminary results, however, indicate that overall environmental impact of bioPA is relatively high, which is primarily due to the use of castor bean oil as the raw material and the bromination of undecenoic acid, involving bromine and acetic acid.

Further guidance provides primarily qualitative rather than quantitative insights into the upstream raw material inputs namely, castor beans for bioPA and maize for bioPC.

On a per-kilogram basis, castor bean production appears to have a higher overall environmental impact than maize. This difference between castor beans and maize is largely attributable to the lower agricultural yield of castor bean production compared to maize grain production, which is cultivated at a much larger scale with more optimised agricultural systems. The lower yield of castor beans typically translates into a relatively higher fertiliser input for castor bean cultivation compared to maize. However, as mentioned before, the agricultural practices surrounding the cultivation of crops in general largely influences their environmental burdens. For example, the adoption of regenerative agricultural practices could substantially reduce the impacts associated with both crops. This should be considered when evaluating or selecting bio-based materials.

Nevertheless, the issue of competition with food production is more pressing for maize, which is a staple food and feed crop, while castor oil is primarily used in industrial applications such as soaps, lubricant and coating. This distinction is relevant in a broader sustainability context, although this is not fully captured by this LCA method. In a similar vein, land use remains a critical concern when shifting from fossil-based to bio-based resources. As a general principle, efforts should be made to utilise agricultural residues, by-products and waste streams as feedstock sources whenever possible and environmentally justified. This strategy can help reduce the pressures associated with land use and mitigate environmental trade-off associated with large-scale bio-based production.

Another factor contributing to the higher impact of bioPA is the higher quantity of castor bean input that is required to obtain 1 kg of bioPA. Based on Öztürk et al. (2014), an average oil yield of 0.47 kg oil per kg castor bean is assumed, hence approximately 2.12 kg of castor beans are required to obtain 1 kg castor oil. In comparison, for maize starch production 1.26 kg of maize grain is required to yield 1 kg of starch. This difference in feedstock demands contributes to the higher overall impact of bioPA in the assessment.

2.2.3 Fossil- and bio-based PET

The production of bio-based polyethylene terephthalate (bioPET), derived from sugarcane was considered for this project as a replacement for conventional PET.

Bio-based PET is a chemically identical alternative to conventional PET. All final stages of its production process are the same as those for conventional PET, meaning it can be processed using existing manufacturing infrastructure. The primary distinction lies in the use of conventional monoethylene glycol (MEG) or bio-based MEG.

The final polymerisation step for both conventional PET and bioPET involves combining purified terephthalic acid (PTA) with monoethylene glycol (MEG) in a precise stoichiometric ratio to form polyethylene terephthalate (PET) polymer chains. This stage of the process, including the energy inputs and the release of water as a byproduct, is identical regardless of whether the MEG is derived from fossil or bio-based sources. Consequently, the resulting bioPET product is chemically and physically indistinguishable from conventional PET. However, since PTA remains petrochemically sourced, bioPET is currently only around 30% bio-based by mass.

The only major difference in the entire value chain is the production of bio-ethylene from bio-ethanol, which is then used to create bio-MEG. Bio-ethylene is produced through catalytic dehydration of bio-ethanol. Conventional ethylene is produced through steam cracking, an extremely high-temperature and energy-intensive process. It uses hydrocarbon feedstocks like naphtha or ethane derived from fossil fuels as the primary raw materials. Further details on the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of PET and bioPET are provided in **Annex A** (5.1.4).

2.2.3.1 Environmental performance of fossil-based and bio-based PET

Figure 5 illustrates the environmental performance of both fossil-based PET and bio-based PET. Similar to the bio-based materials described above, impacts related to agricultural practices, such as acidification, eutrophication, and land use, are higher for the bio-based variant. Other differences are less pronounced, likely due to the fact that bioPET is only approximately 30% bio-based, as PTA remains petrochemically derived.

Nevertheless, the partial substitution of fossil-based inputs is reflected in lower impacts for bioPET in categories such as climate change and fossil resource use. Overall, however, the environmental benefits of reduced fossil dependency are largely offset by the additional burdens associated with biomass cultivation, resulting in no clear overall advantage between PET and bioPET across impact categories.

Figure 5: Environmental performance of PET (1 kg) and bioPET (1kg). The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile of the two synthesis pathways across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. solvent, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey. PTA: purified terephthalic acid

2.2.4 Discussion and Conclusion

Overall, the exploration of bio-based alternatives highlights the importance of trade-offs. It is therefore key to not merely focus on one impact category but apply a holistic view. While being a potential route to reduce impact, the fact that these materials are bio-based does not necessarily imply that their environmental burdens are reduced. Solutions that diminish burdens in certain impact areas often provoke impacts in other areas, so-called trade-offs. For example, impacts like land use and eutrophication which are associated with agricultural practices are often increased when moving towards bio-based resources.

A limitation of the current assessments is that they only look at the impact of the production of the materials. Some alternative bio-based polymers differ in their chemical structure from the conventional plastics. Consequently, these materials behave differently in the recycling process compared to the conventional plastics. In that perspective, alternative bio-based materials that are not drop-in materials, like bioPET, are often not warmly welcomed by recyclers. Thus end-of-life management remains suboptimal with associated consequences.

When exploring alternative materials, it is essential to consider the diversification of input sources to prevent overreliance on any single feedstock. A narrow dependence, particularly on crop-based inputs, can lead to supply risks, land-use pressure, and unintended consequences such as monoculture expansion, agricultural intensification and competition with food. Ideally, alternative materials should be sourced from waste streams or industrial by-products, thereby avoiding competition with food production and land use. In line with Lansink's

ladder, the use of virgin raw materials should be regarded as a last resort and avoided wherever possible.

While the search for more sustainably sourced materials is an approach that is promising, this poses questions in terms of the associated trade-offs and should not be simply considered the go-to solution. Nevertheless, under the right circumstances, tailored to their systemic context, these can aid the transition towards more circular and sustainable products.

2.3 Recycled materials

Besides the use of sustainably sourced bio-based materials, the use of recycled materials is considered an eco-design parameter within the context of the ESPR. The use of recycled materials is key in respect to reducing the need for virgin materials and the mitigation of waste generation together with the related environmental burdens.

While recycling is a key mitigation approach, these processes also induce environmental pressures. Hence benefits as well as burdens are created. Within the context of LCA these should be properly allocated. The most common allocation approaches are presented in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6: Common approaches to allocate impacts and credits from recycled content and recycling processes in LCA between consecutive product cycles. Adopted from (Corona et al., 2019)

Within the context of UNICORN project, the '100:0 or cut-off at recycling' method is applied. This approach is implemented through the 'allocation, cut-off by classification' system model, which adheres to the polluter-pays-principle, and incentivises the use of recycled materials. (Ecoinvent, 2025)

More specifically, recyclable materials are burden-free when they enter recycling processes. When the recycled materials are used in a product, only the environmental impacts from the recycling processes (such as energy use) are attributed to that product at the beginning of its life cycle. In contrast, the environmental impacts associated with the primary extraction and production of these materials are not assigned to the product containing the recycled content. (Ecoinvent, 2025)

At the end-of-life phase, the system boundary is drawn before the recycling process begins. As such, both the environmental burdens as well as benefits of recycling are cut-off and transferred to the next product system that uses the recycled materials. (Ecoinvent, 2025)

In cases where waste materials are incinerated with energy recovery, the cut-off model, as implemented in the Ecoinvent database, does not allocate any credits for the generated energy. Instead, the model distinguishes between waste and recyclables. Waste producers do

not receive any credit for potential reuse or energy recovery of materials arising from waste treatment. For example, heat generated through the incineration of municipal solid waste can be used for the heating of houses and buildings and therefore holds value. Nevertheless, using the cut-off model, the incineration is allocated completely to the treatment of the waste; therefore, the burden remains with the waste producer, while the resulting heat is considered burden-free for the receiving system (Ecoinvent, 2025).

The next sections offer guidance related to the use of recycled materials. Throughout the UNICORN project the use of recycled materials was considered in two different applications namely, the use of recycled PET as substrate for printing and the use of recycled silver (Ag) to replace primary Ag in conductive ink.

The environmental impact is again presented per 1 kg of material. Most substrates examined in the UNICORN case studies can be replaced one-to-one with their recycled counterpart, however, this may vary depending on the design context. For metals used in printing inks, a direct substitution is less straightforward and should, in principle, be considered in the comparison. Since substitution rates vary depending on the design context, we have opted for a per-kilogram comparison. It is up to the user to translate this into impacts for the material requirements of their specific design context.

2.3.1 Virgin and recycled PET

The polymer polyethylene terephthalate (PET) is a widely used saturated polyester produced through the polymerisation of terephthalic acid and ethylene glycol. As the consumption of PET, and polymer materials in general, has surged in a broad range of industries and applications throughout the past decades, this has led to severe environmental pressures like plastic pollution.

Recycling of PET is a key solution in the mitigation of the plastic waste management crisis. The most common method for PET recycling is mechanical recycling which involves the collection and sorting of plastic waste, size reduction through shredding and washing. The obtained clean PET flakes can be melted and moulded into new products.

The term 'recycled materials' can refer to materials with different recycling origins. It is important to distinguish between post-consumer recycled materials (PCR) which, as the name implies, are derived from post-consumer waste (PCW) originating from products that have already been used. While pre-consumer or post-industrial recycled (PIR) materials are derived from post-industrial waste (PIW) which is generated during manufacturing or processing and before the product reaches its intended use phase. In the UNICORN project the impact of PCR and PIR PET are critically assessed.

2.3.1.1 The environmental performance of PET and recycled PET

Using the cut-off method (**Figure 6**), a comparison is made between virgin PET and post-consumer recycled PET (pcrPET) (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7: Relative environmental performance of 1 kg virgin PET and 1 kg recycled PET (pcrPET). The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile of the both virgin PET and pcrPET across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. solvent, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey. PTA: purified terephthalic acid

A strong reduction in impact for pcrPET is observed relative to the PET impact (%). For virgin PET, the highest impacts originate from PET's building blocks namely, terephthalic acid and ethylene glycol, which are both derived from fossil-based resources. Consequently, this results in high impacts related to climate change and fossil-based resource use. For pcrPET the main contributors are related to energy consumption required for the sorting steps and the energy consumption to obtain granulates from sorted PET. Furthermore, unprocessed materials, like missorted fractions or contaminants, that are directed to waste also contribute to the overall impact. The high energy consumption entails climate change to be the highest contributor to the single score impact, however its contribution is still 50 % lower than the climate change impact of virgin PET.

2.3.1.2 The environmental performance of post-consumer and post-industrial PET

Post-industrial waste, opposite to post-consumer waste, is often not considered as waste, but rather as a by-product of joint production (Schulte et al., 2023). Since PIR is derived from pre-consumer by-products, it does not fully close the material loop but preserves materials that cannot be reused directly within the same production process. PIR only applies when post-industrial waste is collected and recycled into raw material that could be used in other manufacturing processes or plants, not just reintroduced into the same line as part of normal production. (Nessi, S. et al., 2021)

In contrast, PCR uses PCW that originates from products after use, closing the loop at a products' end-of-life. Hence, while the use of recyclates obtained from End-of-Life (EoL) products is essential to address the waste crisis, virgin production should be optimised to

minimise the generation of post-industrial waste. Furthermore, the recycled content targets established by EU regulations, like the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), explicitly apply to recycle obtained from post-consumer waste^b, while PIR is not mentioned in this context (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2025).

Therefore, PIR is regarded as by-product within the context of this study and the impacts associated with the production of the virgin PET are partially allocated to the PET scrap based on economic allocation, using market prices. This is in line with the allocation procedures described in ISO 14044 for cases where physical relationships (e.g., mass or energy content) are not the most appropriate basis. According to ISO 14044, allocation can be based on physical properties, economic value or number of subsequent uses of a material. (ISO, 2006)

Currently, the average price for PIR PET is €0.53/kg, while virgin PET is priced at approximately €1.20/kg (Plasticker.de; accessed 14.04.2025). Following economic allocation, this means that the total impact of the PET production process is allocated for 70% to the resulting virgin PET and for 30% to the post-industrial PET scrap byproduct.

Due to a lack of inventory data for the recycling process of PIR, an assumption for its impacts has been made based on the market price. It is considered that the market price reflects the complexity of the recycling process, inputs such as washing and sorting are scaled accordingly. With an average market price of 1.20 EUR/kg for pcrPET and 0.53 EUR/kg for pirPET, this implies that the process-related inputs for PIR are reduced by 56%, reflecting its lower processing burden compared to PCR. **Table 5** in Annex A shows the considered inventories and, if relevant, the adjusted material inputs for virgin PET and recycled PET.

Figure 8 compares the environmental performance of virgin PET with that of pcrPET and pirPET. The overall single-score impact is highest for virgin PET, followed by pirPET and pcrPET. This difference is mainly driven by climate change and fossil-based resource use, categories in which virgin PET shows the highest impacts mainly due to its petrochemical origin. Similarly, at the level of individual impact categories, virgin PET is the dominant contributor across almost all categories, with the exception of cancer-related toxicity and land use. However, these exceptions contribute only marginally to the overall single score of the different PET options.

In summary, although recycling processes also generate environmental burdens, the savings achieved by avoiding virgin material production are significantly larger. It should be noted, however, that these results are sensitive to the choice of allocation method, which can influence the relative performance of the recycled materials.

^b PPWR definition: 'post-consumer plastic waste' means waste that is plastic and that has been generated from plastic products that have been placed on the market or supplied for distribution, consumption or use in a third country in the course of a commercial activity, whether in return for payment or free of charge

Figure 8: Environmental performance of 1 kg virgin PET, pirPET and pcrPET. The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile of the three PET types across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. chemical factory, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey. PTA: purified terephthalic acid; pcrPET: post-consumer polyethylene terephthalate; pirPET: post-industrial polyethylene terephthalate; piw: post-industrial waste; pcw: post-consumer waste.

2.3.2 Virgin and recycled Silver

As mentioned in section 1.2, secondary metals have the potential to strongly reduce environmental burdens associated with extraction and refining. Within the context of the UNICORN project the use of recycled silver (rAg) in conductive inks is investigated. Various percentages of recycled silver are applied across the different use cases.

2.3.2.1 Environmental performance of recycled Ag

Figure 9 illustrates the environmental impacts of the global market average of silver compared to the impact of 1 kg secondary Ag recovered exclusively from electronic scrap. For the analysis theecoinvent record for market Ag ('Silver {GLO}| market for silver | Cut-off, U'). Recycled Ag is approximated by omitting the inputs derived from primary extraction together with their associated transport. The secondary-sourced inputs, and their transport, were scaled to amount to the original weight of the market silver.

Figure 9: Relative environmental performance of market silver (Ag) versus secondary silver (rAg). The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. chemical factory, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey.

The results show that the single score impact of market-average silver is more than 100 times higher than that of recycled silver (rAg). This difference is primarily driven by mineral and metal resource use, which accounts for approximately 94% of the total single score impact of market-average silver. When excluded, other important impact categories appear such as climate change (20%), freshwater ecotoxicity (19%) and fossil-based resource use (12%).

Overall, market-average silver exhibits the highest impacts across nearly all impact categories compared to recycled silver, with the exception of human toxicity (cancer and non-cancer), where rAg scores higher. This higher human toxicity impact for rAg is attributable to the recycling process, specifically to the formation of copper slag. During smelting, impurities such as lead, arsenic, and cadmium are captured in the slag. If this slag is improperly handled or disposed of, these substances can contribute significantly to human toxicity. In the database, copper slag from the recycling process is assumed to be landfilled as a residual material. While (copper) slag is also generated in the other silver production processes that make up the market average, the relative human toxicity impact for rAg is higher because the impact is calculated per kilogram of rAg, rather than across the entire production mix represented in the market average.

2.3.3 Discussion and Conclusion

Throughout this study, the recycled materials considered generally show lower environmental burdens due to the application of the cut-off method.

While the environmental benefits of using post-consumer recycled PET are clear, the results for pirPET are more nuanced. Post-industrial recyclate should be regarded as a by-product, receiving part of the burdens of the PET production.

However, accurately assessing the impact of PIR remains challenging. In this study, economic allocation is applied, as physical allocation is not feasible. This choice is in line with ISO 14044, which states that when allocation cannot be based on a physical relationship (e.g., mass, energy content), other relevant relationships, such as economic value, may be used. This method reflects complex attributes of product or service quality that cannot be easily measured by physical criteria. Nevertheless, market prices can fluctuate significantly, which may introduce variability into the results. For this reason, the allocation approach is transparently documented in section 2.3.1.2.

Recycled silver (rAg) shows a substantially lower environmental impact than market-average silver, mainly due to reduced resource depletion and lower impacts across most categories. The main trade-off lies in higher human toxicity potential from slag management, underlining the importance of proper waste treatment practices.

2.4 Use of different materials

Both copper (Cu) and silver (Ag) are widely used as conductive metals across a broad range of applications and across the different use cases considered throughout this project. While both metals fulfil similar functional roles in terms of conductivity, their production pathways, extraction methods, and associated environmental burdens can differ substantially. These differences arise not only from variations in ore grade, mining scale, and processing technologies, but also from the distinct chemical properties of each metal, which influence refining processes and the use of auxiliary substances. In addition, their respective global production volumes vary greatly, which can affect the overall scale of their environmental footprint. (Bachér T. et al., 2020)

In certain applications throughout the UNICORN project, aluminium is considered as an alternative to silver. Although aluminium has a lower electrical conductivity than silver, it is significantly lighter and more abundant, making it attractive for weight-sensitive or cost-constrained applications.

The following section examines and compares the environmental performance of primary copper, primary silver and primary aluminium per kg metal. Note, however, that if a one-to-one replacement is not technically feasible, the resulting change in material inputs should be accounted for in the analysis. For the analysis, theecoinvent records for 'Silver {GLO}| market for silver | Cut-off, U', 'Copper, cathode {GLO}| market for copper, cathode | Cut-off, U' together and 'Aluminium, primary, ingot {GLO}| market for | Cut-off, U' were considered. As primary sourced metals are considered, these are approximated by omitting the secondary sourced inputs from the market average together with their associated transport. The primary extraction inputs, and their transport, were scaled to amount to the original weight of the market mix.

2.4.1 Silver and copper

Figure 10: Environmental performance of 1 kg primary silver (Ag) and 1 kg primary copper (Cu). The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. chemical factory, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey.

Based on the results presented in **Figure 10**, primary silver shows the highest impact across all assessed impact categories. The overall impact (single score) of silver is predominantly driven by metals- and minerals-related resource use which contributes 94%, stemming from silver–gold mining and refining. This impact is roughly two orders of magnitude higher than that of copper. Since silver is produced from copper ores (17%), lead ores (28%) and gold–silver ores (34%), one contributing factor is the generally lower ore grades of silver compared to copper, which require more intensive mining, beneficiation, and concentration processes to obtain equivalent amounts of metal (Nuss and Eckelman, 2014).

When resource use is excluded from the analysis, other notable contributors to silver’s single score impact include climate change, ecotoxicity, and fossil resource use. These impacts reflect the combined effects of energy-intensive processing, the use of auxiliary chemicals, and potential pollutant releases during extraction, refining and waste management (Reuter M. et al., 2013). As discussed in section 2.3.2, primary metal production is particularly energy-intensive during the refining stage, which often involves precisely controlled melting operations that rely heavily on fossil fuels, either directly as a reductant or indirectly for heat and electricity (Reuter M. et al., 2013). This is also evident in this analysis, where silver shows higher impacts related to both climate change and fossil-based resource use.

Silver’s ecotoxicity is largely linked to leaching from sulphidic tailings, a mechanism that also contributes to copper’s ecotoxicity. From a biological perspective, silver is generally considered a toxic, non-essential element for most plants and animals, including humans. In contrast,

copper is an essential micronutrient required in trace amounts for the proper functioning of certain enzymes and other physiological processes. While copper can become toxic when concentrations exceed biological tolerance thresholds, silver is inherently toxic, even at relatively low concentrations, due to its ability to disrupt cellular processes. In general, silver is one of the most toxic metals to aquatic life in laboratory experiments and is listed under Annex XVII to the REACH (SCRREEN, 2023c). This inherent toxicity is one of the main reasons why silver is widely used in antibacterial applications.

2.4.2 Silver and aluminium

Figure 11 shows the environmental performance of 1 kg primary aluminium compared to 1 kg primary silver.

Figure 11: Environmental performance of 1 kg primary silver (Ag) and 1 kg primary aluminium (Al). The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors are highlighted, while less significant contributors (e.g. chemical factory, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey.

Similar to the results described in section 2.4.1, resource use related to metals and minerals accounts for 94% of the total single score impact of primary silver production. When this impact category is excluded, the remaining significant contributors are climate change (20%), freshwater ecotoxicity (19%), and fossil-based resource use (12%).

In contrast, the environmental impact of primary aluminium production is only a fraction of that of primary silver. The main impact categories contributing to the single score for aluminium are climate change (37%), particulate matter formation (17%), and fossil-based resource use (16%). These impacts are largely driven by the electricity mix used during production, which in

this case is primarily based on hard coal, reflecting aluminium smelting activities predominantly located in China for this analysis.

As with the earlier comparison between copper and silver, the disproportionately high impact of silver is primarily due to its very low concentration in ores, typically extracted as a by-product from lead, zinc, copper, or gold mining. In contrast, aluminium (extracted from bauxite) benefits from much higher ore concentrations as bauxite typically contains more than 40% aluminium oxide significantly reducing the environmental burden per kilogram of metal (SCRREEN, 2023a).

2.4.3 Aluminium and copper

Figure 12: Environmental performance of 1 kg copper (Cu) and 1 kg aluminium (Al). The upper panels show (1) the comparative environmental profile across individual impact categories, normalised to the highest contributor in each impact category (set at 100%, right-side bars), and (2) the relative contribution of each impact category to the overall single score (left-side bars, grey colour). The lower panel presents the single score results per synthesis pathway, broken down by contributions from specific process steps. The dominant contributors are highlighted, while less significant contributions (e.g. chemical factory, heat, electricity, water) are grouped and displayed in grey.

As shown in **Figure 12**, the overall environmental impact (single score) of primary copper (Cu) is approximately ten times higher than that of primary aluminium (Al). This result is largely driven by the impact category of metal and mineral resource depletion. When this category is excluded, the leading impact categories for copper are human toxicity (37%) and acidification (22%), whereas for aluminium, the dominant impacts to climate change (19%), particulate matter formation (8%), and fossil-based resource use (8%) become apparent.

A key reason for the higher impact of copper lies again in the ore concentration differences. Bauxite, the primary ore for aluminium, typically contains more than 40% alumina (Al_2O_3), while copper ores usually contain only 0.5% to 3% Cu (SCRREEN, 2023b, 2023a). Consequently,

significantly more ore must be mined and processed to obtain the same quantity of copper, increasing energy use, waste generation, and associated emissions.

The smelting of copper concentrate is a particularly impactful stage in terms of both acidification and human toxicity. Following mining, copper ore is crushed, ground, and concentrated through flotation, increasing the copper content to around 25–35%. This concentrate is then smelted to produce “matte”, which contains 50–70% copper. Final purification is achieved via pyrometallurgical processes (smelting and electrolytic refining) or hydrometallurgical processes (leaching, solvent extraction, and electrowinning). The pyrometallurgical route is especially associated with sulphur dioxide (SO₂) emissions, which contribute substantially to acidification and photochemical ozone formation. (SCRREEN, 2023b)

In addition, slag treatment and the handling of tailings, especially from sulphidic ores, pose risks to human and environmental health. Poorly managed tailings can lead to acid mine drainage and heavy metal leaching, with long-term effects on surrounding ecosystems. This is particularly concerning given that approximately 85% of global copper ores are sulphidic. Some deposits may also involve low-level radioactive exposure, notably in regions such as China, the United States, and the Democratic Republic of Congo. (SCRREEN, 2023b)

As previously mentioned, the processing steps for aluminium are highly energy-intensive. Primary aluminium is produced through the electrolytic reduction of alumina (aluminium oxide, Al₂O₃) using the Hall-Héroult process, in which alumina is dissolved in molten cryolite and then electrolysed to yield molten aluminium metal. On average, producing one tonne of aluminium requires approximately 15,000 kilowatt-hours of electricity and 1.9 tonnes of alumina. (SCRREEN, 2023a)

This intensive energy demand reflected in the higher environmental impacts observed in the categories of climate change, particulate matter formation, and fossil-based resource use. These impacts are strongly influenced by the electricity mix used in the smelting process, which, in this analysis, is assumed to be primarily based on hard coal, reflecting aluminium production that is largely situated in China.

2.4.4 Conclusion

It can be concluded that the environmental impact of primary silver is considerable, not only due to the energy- and material-intensive nature of its extraction and refining, driven by its low concentration in ores, but also due to its toxicity potential as reflected by the impact in freshwater ecotoxicity.

Where technically feasible, the use of alternative metals with lower environmental impacts should be considered. In particular, copper and aluminium can partially or fully substitute silver in many electrical and electronic applications, depending on conductivity, corrosion resistance, and application-specific requirements. In some high-performance use cases, other precious metals (e.g. gold or palladium) may also serve as functional alternatives, although their environmental impacts and cost must be carefully evaluated.

Nonetheless, it is important to note that these findings are only valid if the alternative metal can be used in comparable amounts. If higher quantities are required to achieve similar performance (due to lower conductivity or different physical properties), the impacts should be scaled accordingly in the assessment to avoid underestimating the total burden.

Ultimately, material substitution decisions should consider not only functional equivalence but also life cycle trade-offs, including resource depletion, climate impact, and toxicity. End-of-life recovery potential and recycling efficiency of the substitute metals should also be factored into the overall sustainability evaluation.

2.5 Critical raw materials

To further substantiate the guidance provided in section 2.4 regarding the choice of metals it is important to consider material criticality.

Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) are defined by the European Commission (Grohol M. and Veeh C., 2023) as materials that have a high supply risk and are at the same time of significant economic importance. More specifically, the economic importance of a material is determined based on the value added of the relevant EU manufacturing sectors corrected with a substitution index as reducing factor and the supply risk is determined based on global and EU supply concentration weighted by a governance performance index and corrected by recycling and substitution parameters. The first assessment was conducted in 2011 and updated every three years. The study of 2023 identified 34 raw materials as critical from a list of 87 individual raw materials in total. (Grohol M. and Veeh C., 2023). Annex C provides an overview of the identified critical raw materials.

Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) are typically produced and consumed in relatively small quantities, yet they possess unique properties that make them indispensable in a wide range of strategic technologies, including renewable energy, digital infrastructure, aerospace, and defence. Notable examples include rare earth elements used in the permanent magnets of wind turbine motors, lithium for battery production, and high-purity silicon for the manufacturing of semiconductors. It should be noted that the Critical Raw Material Act contains a list of Strategic Raw Materials (SRMs) as well. These Strategic Raw Materials (SRMs) are of critical importance to the functioning of the internal market, particularly due to their essential role in strategic technologies that support the green and digital transitions, as well as in defence and aerospace sectors. They are characterised by a potentially significant mismatch between global supply and projected demand, and their production is often difficult to scale up rapidly, primarily due to long lead times associated with developing new extraction or processing capacity. To reflect evolving technological and economic conditions, the list of SRMs should be regularly reviewed and updated as needed. The identified SRMs are added to the list of CRMs.

As a general principle, the use of CRMs should be avoided or minimised wherever possible to reduce supply chain vulnerability and support long-term material resilience. In line with this, graphite was successfully omitted in certain UNICORN functional electronics, thereby lowering the inflow of critical materials. In other cases, such as the substitution of silver, which is not critical, with copper or aluminium, the environmental performance was substantially improved, as demonstrated in sections 2.4.1 and 2.4.2, but the critical material inflow increased.

To balance both environmental impact and material criticality, the preferred eco-design approach is to take into consideration the use of secondary (recycled) metals. This strategy has the potential to reduce lifecycle environmental burdens while also alleviating pressure on primary critical raw material supply. Material selection decisions should therefore be guided by a combined assessment of circularity including criticality, and environmental impact, ensuring a holistic and future-proof product design.

3 Conclusions & Perspectives

This eco-design guidelines report shows that targeted material improvements introduced at the design stage can significantly enhance the environmental performance and circularity potential of functional electronics in smart systems. Material optimisation is identified as a key strategy with distinct advantages when critically assessed, but the report also stresses the importance of adopting a holistic approach that accounts for potential trade-offs, not only in terms of environmental impact but also from a circularity perspective.

In addition to material choices, strategies such as product lifetime extension, process optimisation, and reuse can further strengthen circularity potential. However, these measures are highly context-dependent and must be tailored to each specific system, as practices and system characteristics strongly influence their effectiveness. For this reason, such measures are not discussed in detail in this guidance. Nevertheless, in most cases the greatest benefits are achieved when these strategies are applied in combination rather than in isolation.

Concerning the trade-offs mentioned above, material choices remain central to eco-design. The use of recycled materials, bio-based polymers, and secondary metals provides tangible benefits in reducing reliance on virgin non-renewable resources. However, these measures also highlight the risk of burden shifting, as environmental gains in one impact category may be offset by increases in others, such as land use or water consumption. The report stresses that such trade-offs must be systematically evaluated to avoid unintended consequences. Moreover, trade-offs are not restricted to environmental impacts alone but may also relate to other aspects, such as end-of-life performance.

The role of critical raw materials (CRMs) represents both an environmental and strategic dimension. Functional electronics, and electronics in general, are increasingly dependent on materials with supply risks or high geopolitical sensitivity. The report identifies substitution, recycling, and minimisation of CRM use as essential design considerations. While substitution options may be limited due to technical constraints, recycling and circular business models offer a promising pathway for mitigating supply risks while aligning with circularity objectives.

While these targeted improvements are key, they must be complemented with system-level thinking. Eco-design cannot be addressed only at the component level but must be embedded within the broader product and system architecture. This requires alignment of design decisions with value chain partners, manufacturing processes, and end-of-life management infrastructure. Cross-sectoral collaboration is essential to ensure that eco-design measures are not only technically feasible but also practically implementable at scale.

In practice, eco-design should be treated as a multi-dimensional optimisation challenge, where environmental, technical, economic, and social aspects are weighed together. Early integration of eco-design principles into the innovation and development process is particularly critical, as opportunities for material substitution, but also design for recyclability and reuse, are much harder to implement once the product architecture is fixed.

The findings of this report confirm that eco-design measures can play a decisive role in advancing the sustainability of functional electronics in smart systems. While challenges remain, particularly around trade-offs, the results indicate that strategies centred on recycled materials, bio-based polymers, and secondary metals can be highly effective when applied holistically and tailored to the system in question. In particular, emphasis should be placed on the use of secondary materials and second-generation feedstock, as these help to mitigate trade-offs not only in terms of environmental impacts but also regarding material criticality. By embedding these measures early in product development and fostering collaboration across the value chain, eco-design can deliver significant progress toward the objectives of a circular and resource-efficient economy.

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5 Annexes

5.1 Annex A: Life cycle inventories and additional background information

5.1.1 Fossil-based polycarbonate

Bisphenol A is typically synthesised through the acid-catalysed condensation of phenol and acetone (Pressman and Wetzel, 2001). These two building blocks are both derived from petrochemical resources, with phenol primarily produced via the cumene process (which involves benzene and propylene, both obtained from crude oil or natural gas), and acetone being a byproduct of this same process. Since both precursors originate from fossil-based feedstocks, conventional BPA production remains heavily reliant on petrochemical resources. (Mooij D. and Muller M.A., 2021)

During PC synthesis, the phosgene reacts with BPA to form polycarbonate chains. This reaction is conducted in the presence of the solvent methylene chlorine (dichloromethane, DCM), which also poses significant risk to human health and the environment. (Mooij D. and Muller M.A., 2021)

Phosgene is synthesised through the reaction of carbon monoxide (CO) and chlorine gas (Cl₂) in the presence of activated carbon catalyst. (Mooij D. and Muller M.A., 2021)

For the analysis 'Polycarbonate {RoW}| polycarbonate production | Cut-off, U' represents the conventional PC synthesis from BPA and phosgene. For the non-phosgene synthesis route the phosgene input is exchanged by diphenyl carbonate which is approximated by the reaction between DMC ('Dimethyl carbonate {GLO}| market for dimethyl carbonate | Cut-off, U and phenol') and phenol ('Phenol {RoW}| market for phenol | Cut-off, U') in the presence of 'Sodium methoxide {GLO}| market for sodium methoxide | Cut-off, U'.

For the approximation of reagents auxiliary records concerning energy consumption, water use and waste of the chemical factory are taken into account to achieve a realistic approximation of the production process. The main source of information for the values for heat, electricity, water (process and cooling), nitrogen, chemical factory is industry data from the GENDORF Chemical Park. The values are a 5-year average of data from 2015 to 2019 published by the GENDORF Chemical Park, which is based in Germany and produced an average of 2462760 tonnes of chemical substances in the years 2015-2019.

Chemical factory inputs are approximated based on literature data published by the GENDORF Chemical Park (Gendorf, Umwelterklärung, www.gendorf.de).

Table 2: Life cycle inventory of fossil-based polycarbonate focusing on material input flows

Material	Weight or amount	Unit	Data record (Ecoinvent, else specified)	Comment
Input flows				
Bisphenol A	0,916	kg	Bisphenol A, powder {GLO} market for bisphenol A, powder Cut-off, U	
Phosgene	0,39691	kg	Phosgene, liquid {RoW} market for phosgene, liquid Cut-off, U	
Sodium hydroxide	0,320985	kg	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	
Output flow				
Biobased PC	1	kg		

5.1.2 Bio-based polycarbonate

For the production of bio-based polycarbonate this synthesis pathway was approximated by a phosgene and non-phosgene route as explained below.

Isosorbide is viewed as one of the most promising bio-based alternatives for BPA. It is typically produced from sorbitol under acid conditions, for this sulfuric acid 'Sulfuric acid {RoW}| market for sulfuric acid | Cut-off, U' was considered in the model. The non-phosgene melt transesterification route for polycarbonate synthesis involves the reaction with diphenyl carbonate (DPC) which is described above.

In this study, glucose (Glucose {GLO}| market for glucose | Cut-off, U) derived from maize starch (Maize starch {GLO}| market for maize starch | Cut-off, U) is used as starting material for the production of isosorbide used for the production of bioPC as this inventory data is available in Ecoinvent. The life cycle inventory data for maize starch production are based on the study (Würdinger E. et al., 2003) which reflects starch production processes commonly used in Germany. The process includes several key steps: transport of maize grains with 14% moisture content, mechanical cleaning, soaking in warm water, milling and separation of the germ (used to produce corn oil), starch extraction, drying to a final moisture content of 14%, and recovery of by-products such as maize gluten and maize-gluten feed.

Wastewater treatment is included via defined modules for maize starch effluent, although emissions to air or solid waste are considered negligible. Allocation of impacts was performed on an economic basis, with maize starch accounting for 83% of total earnings from the process, and the remaining 17% allocated to by-products. This inventory forms the basis for modelling maize starch in life cycle assessments where no more specific data are available.

Isosorbide is typically synthesised from sorbitol, a sugar alcohol conventionally obtained through the catalytic hydrogenation of glucose (Glucose {GLO} | market for glucose | Cut-off, U) using gaseous hydrogen (Hydrogen, gaseous {GLO} | market for hydrogen, gaseous | Cut-off, U). This hydrogenation reaction is commonly performed in the presence of a nickel-based catalyst, such as Raney nickel (Nickel, class 1 {GLO} | market for nickel, class 1 | Cut-off, U) (García et al., 2021, 2024; Romero et al., 2017).

Table 3: Life cycle inventory of biobased polycarbonate focussing on material input flows

Material	Weight or amount	Unit	Data record (Ecoinvent, else specified)	Comment
Input flows related to 1 kg bioPC output				
Isosorbide	405,6	g	Proxy	See input materials below
Diphenyl carbonate (DPC)	594,4	g	Proxy	See input materials below
Sodium methoxide	10	g	Sodium methoxide {GLO} market for sodium methoxide Cut-off, U	Assumed a catalyst concentration of 1%
Input flows related to 1 kg isosorbide output				
Sorbitol	1246,05	g	Proxy	See input materials below
Sulfuric acid	12,46	g	Sulfuric acid {RoW} market for sulfuric acid Cut-off, U	Assumed a catalyst concentration of 1%
Input flows related to 1 kg diphenyl carbonate output				
Phenol	878.3	g	Phenol {RoW} market for phenol Cut-off, U	
Sodium methoxide	8.78	g	Sodium methoxide {GLO} market for sodium methoxide Cut-off, U	Assumed a catalyst concentration of 1%

Dimethyl carbonate (DMC)	420.6	g	Dimethyl carbonate {GLO} market for dimethyl carbonate Cut-off, U	
Input flows related to 1 kg sorbitol output				
Hydrogen	11.09	g	Hydrogen, gaseous {GLO} market for hydrogen, gaseous Cut-off, U	
Glucose	988.1	g	Glucose {GLO} market for glucose Cut-off, U	
Nickel	3.29	g	Nickel, class 1 {GLO} market for nickel, class 1 Cut-off, U	Assumed a catalyst concentration of 1%. However, this catalyst is typically reused in multiple runs. Based on Hoffer - 2003 we assume 3 hydrogenation runs.

5.1.3 Bio-based polyamide

Within the context of this project, PA11 was explored, together with bioPC, as alternative substrate material. This polyamide is synthesised via polycondensation of amino acids and therefore fully bio-based. The synthesis process starts with the extraction and refining of castor bean oil, the shells of the beans are removed followed by mechanical pressing to obtain the triglycerides (oil). The subsequent saponification (or transesterification) step affords ricinoleic acid, the primary fatty acid component. Through pyrolytic cleavage, ricinoleic acid is converted into 10-undecenoic acid, a key intermediate for the production of 11-aminoundecanoic acid. The latter is obtained via bromination and subsequent amination. Finally, the obtained monomer subsequently undergoes polycondensation to form bio-based polyamide 11 (PA11, nylon 11). (Winnacker M. and Reiger B., 2016; Farahat M., 2021)

In this study, the bio-based PA11 synthesis route was approximated and evaluated in comparison with bioPC and conventional PC. Bio-based PA11 will hereafter be referred to as bioPA. A description of the life cycle inventory together with material input flows selected for the synthesis of bioPA are provided in **Table 4**.

In this study, it is assumed that fatty acids are obtained from castor oil via a saponification process, as described by (Zhang et al., 2013). Due to the lack of specific life cycle inventory (LCI) data in literature, modified Ecoinvent processes are used as proxies to represent both castor oil production and saponification. For the oil production step, the process 'Cottonseed oil, crude {IN} | cottonseed oil mill operation | Cut-off, U' is adapted by substituting the cottonseed input with castor beans, represented by 'Castor bean {IN} | castor bean production | Cut-off, U'. An average oil yield of 0.47 kg per kg of castor beans is assumed, based on the findings of Öztürk et al. (2014). Castor bean yield is known to vary significantly depending on genotype and environmental conditions. For instance, (Pari et al., 2020) reported higher yields, and mentioned other studies with yields ranging from 2000 to 2620 kg/ha in France. Similarly, Anastasi (2015) reported yields between 1790 and 4750 kg/ha when grown in Italy (Anastasi U. et al., 2015). In the current study, a yield of 2800 to 2900 kg/ha is assumed. To reflect this increase in yield compared to the baseline Ecoinvent input (647 kg/ha), the same input inventory is retained, but scaled by a factor of 4.48.

The saponification of castor bean oil is modelled by adapting the process Fatty acid {RoW} | fatty acid production, from soybean oil | Cut-off, U, in which the soybean input is replaced by the castor bean input described above. This process yields ricinoleic acid, which is

subsequently pyrolysed to produce undecenoic acid. Since pyrolysis typically occurs at temperatures between 345 °C and 752 °C, the associated energy inputs are scaled by a factor of 5.5.

The bromination of undecenoic acid is approximated as its reaction with bromine (Bromine {GLO} | market for bromine | Cut-off, U) in the presence of acetic acid (Acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state {GLO} | market for acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state | Cut-off, U). Additional chemical factory inputs are included as specified in section 5.1.1.

The subsequent amination of 11-bromoundecanoic acid is modelled as a reaction with ammonia (Ammonia, anhydrous, liquid {RoW} | market for ammonia, anhydrous, liquid | Cut-off, U), with chemical factory inputs again taken from

This yields 11-aminoundecanoic acid, which undergoes self-condensation polymerisation. In this step, the amine group of one molecule reacts with the carboxylic acid group of another, forming amide bonds (–CONH–) and releasing water as a by-product. Given that polycondensation is typically conducted at 200 °C–250 °C, a scaling factor of 2.5 is applied to the chemical factory inputs related to energy and heat (Martino et al., 2014).

Bio-based PC is modelled as described above (section 5.1.2).

Table 4: Life cycle inventory of bio-based polyamide focussing on material input flows

Material	Weight or amount	Unit	Data record (Ecoinvent, else specified)	Comment
Input flows related to 1 kg bioPA (nylon 11) output				
11-aminoundecanoic acid		g	Proxy	See input materials below
Input flows related to 1 kg 11-aminoundecanoic acid output				
11-bromoundecenoic acid	1.3705	g	Proxy	See input materials below
Ammonia	300	g	Ammonia, anhydrous, liquid {RoW} market for ammonia, anhydrous, liquid Cut-off, U	The stoichiometric amount alone would be around 85 g of ammonia, so using 300 g provides a sufficient excess to ensure a complete reaction.
Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	417,5	g	Dimethyl sulfoxide {GLO} market for dimethyl sulfoxide Cut-off, U	Solvent reagent ratio 5:1. Typically 95-99% DMSO is recovered.
Input flows related to 1 kg 11-bromoundecenoic acid output				
Undecenoic acid	700,3	g	Phenol {RoW} market for phenol Cut-off, U	Based on stoichiometric reaction
Bromine	607	g	Bromine {GLO} market for bromine Cut-off, U	Based on stoichiometric reaction
Acetic acid	4000	g	Acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state {GLO} market for acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state Cut-off, U	1 M solution corresponds to 1 L per mole substrate which is 3.8 mol.
Input flows related to 1 kg undecenoic acid output				

Ricinoleic acid	1620	g	Proxy based on: Fatty acid {RoW} fatty acid production, from soybean oil Cut-off, U With castor bean oil as input instead of cottonseed oil.	Pyrolysis assumed at 550 °C
Input flows related to 1 kg ricinoleic acid output				
Castor bean oil	1032	g	Proxy based on: Cottonseed oil, crude {IN} cottonseed oil mill operation Cut-off, U With Castor bean {RoW} castor bean production Cut-off, U as input material instead of cotton.	

5.1.4 Fossil-based PET

Fossil-based PET was modelled using the record 'Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous {GLO}| market for polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous | Cut-off, U'. Which is derived from ethylene glycol 'Ethylene glycol {GLO}| market for ethylene glycol | Cut-off, U' and 'Purified terephthalic acid {GLO}| market for purified terephthalic acid | Cut-off, U'. Bio-based PET

The production of bio-based PET starts with sugar cane as input material. Through fermentation, ethanol ('Ethanol, without water, in 95% solution state, from fermentation {BR}| ethanol production from sugarcane | Cut-off, U- updated is derived') is derived from sugar cane ('Sugarcane {BR}| market for sugarcane | Cut-off, U'). Next, the dehydration of bio-ethanol in the presence of zeolite catalysts ('Zeolite, powder {RoW}| zeolite production, powder | Cut-off, U') offers bio-ethylene. This dehydration typically occurs at 300°C to 400°C, hence the energy- and heat-related chemical factory inputs (Annex A, 0) are scaled by 3.5. Bio-ethylene serves as input material for the synthesis of ethylene oxide ('Ethylene oxide, bio {RER}| ethylene oxide production, from sugar cane | Cut-off, U') which is converted to mono-ethylene glycol ('Ethylene glycol, bio {RER}| ethylene glycol production, from sugar cane | Cut-off, U'). The obtained bio-MEG is combined with the petrochemical-based PTA ('Purified terephthalic acid {GLO}| market for purified terephthalic acid | Cut-off, U') in the same polymerization process used for conventional PET ('Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous {GLO}| market for polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous | Cut-off, U'). This creates bioPET polymer with a bio-based content of up to 30%.

5.1.5 Life cycle inventory of virgin PET and recycled PET

Table 5: Life cycle inventory of virgin PET, PIR PET and PCR PET

Material	Weight or amount	Unit	Data record (Ecoinvent, else specified)	Comment
Input flows related to 1 kg virgin PET output				
PET, granulate, amorphous	1	kg	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous {RoW} polyethylene terephthalate production, granulate, amorphous Cut-off, U	
Input flows related to 1 kg pcrPET output				
PET, granulate, amorphous, recycled	1	kg	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous, recycled {RoW} polyethylene terephthalate production, granulate, amorphous, recycled Cut-off, U	
Input flows related to 1 kg pirPET – virgin material input economic allocation				
PET, granulate, amorphous	300	g	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous {RoW} polyethylene terephthalate production, granulate, amorphous Cut-off, U	Complemented with recycling process input to approximate PIR impact
pirPET (1 kg) recycling process				
PET, granulate, amorphous, recycled	1	kg	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous, recycled {RoW} polyethylene terephthalate production, granulate, amorphous, recycled Cut-off, U	Adjustments listed below
<i>Adjustments recycling process (b = 0.44)</i>				
Organic chemicals	0,0067	kg	Chemical, organic {GLO} market for chemical, organic Cut-off, U	
Plastic extrusion	4,76*10 ⁻⁷	kg	Extrusion, plastic film {GLO} market for extrusion, plastic film Cut-off, U	

Polypropylene fraction	$4.76 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot b^c$	kg	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for polypropylene, granulate Cut-off, U	Missorted fraction
Soap	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot b^c$	kg	Soap {GLO} market for soap Cut-off, U	Washing step
Sodium hydroxide	$0.024 \cdot b^c$	kg	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	Washing step
Steel	$2,29 \cdot 10^{-8}$	kg	Steel, low-alloyed {GLO} market for steel, low-alloyed Cut-off, U	
Sulfuric acid	$8,396946564886 \cdot 10^{-6}$	kg	Sulfuric acid {RoW} market for sulfuric acid Cut-off, U	
Sorting PET waste	$1,25 \cdot b^c$	kg	Waste polyethylene terephthalate, for recycling, sorted {RoW} market for waste polyethylene terephthalate, for recycling, sorted Cut-off, U	Sorting step inputs are reduced with 56%
PIR input material	1,25	kg	PIR 30% Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous {RoW} polyethylene terephthalate production, granulate, amorphous Cut-off, U	Added the 30% virgin impact.
Waste PE	-0.0009	kg	Waste polyethylene, for recycling, sorted {GLO} waste polyethylene, for recycling, sorted, Recycled Content cut-off Cut-off, U	
Facility	$2,0 \cdot 10^{-9}$	p	Waste preparation facility {GLO} market for waste preparation facility Cut-off, U	
Wire drawing	$2,29 \cdot 10^{-8}$	kg		
Electricity/heat	b^c			Electricity and heat inputs are scaled with the pricing parameter

^c b is set as parameter reflecting the price ratio between PCR and PIR PET that results in a reducing factor

5.2 Annex B: The environmental impact categories of the Product Environmental Footprint methodology

Source: European Commission (2021)

Climate Change/Global Warming Potential (kg CO₂ equivalent)

Capacity of a greenhouse gas to influence radiative forcing, expressed in terms of a reference substance (for example, CO₂-equivalent units) and specified time horizon (e.g. GWP 20, GWP 100, GWP 500, for 20, 100, and 500 years respectively). It relates to the capacity to influence changes in the global average surface-air temperature and subsequent change in various climate parameters and their effects, such as storm frequency and intensity, rainfall intensity and frequency of flooding, etc.

Ozone Depletion (kg CFC-11 equivalent)

EF impact category that accounts for the degradation of stratospheric ozone due to emissions of ozone-depleting substances, for example long-lived chlorine and bromine containing gases (e.g. CFCs, HCFCs, Halons)

Human toxicity: cancer (CTUh)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human beings caused by the intake of toxic substances through inhalation of air, food/water ingestion, penetration through the skin insofar as they are related to cancer.

Human toxicity: non-cancer (CTUh)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human beings caused by the intake of toxic substances through inhalation of air, food/water ingestion, penetration through the skin insofar as they are related to non-cancer effects that are not caused by particulate matter/respiratory inorganics or ionising radiation.

Particulate Matter/Respiratory Inorganics (disease incidence)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human health caused by emissions of Particulate Matter (PM) and its precursors (NO_x, SO_x, NH₃)

Ionising Radiation, human health (kBq U²³⁵ equivalent)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human health caused by radioactive releases.

Photochemical Ozone Formation (kg NMVOC equivalent)

EF impact category that accounts for the formation of ozone at the ground level of the troposphere caused by photochemical oxidation of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) and carbon monoxide (CO) in the presence of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and sunlight. High concentrations of ground-level tropospheric ozone damage vegetation, human respiratory tracts and manmade materials through reaction with organic materials.

Acidification (mol H⁺ equivalent)

EF impact category that addresses impacts due to acidifying substances in the environment. Emissions of NO_x, NH₃ and SO_x lead to releases of hydrogen ions (H⁺) when the gases are mineralised. The protons contribute to the acidification of soils and water when they are

released in areas where the buffering capacity is low, resulting in forest decline and lake acidification.

Eutrophication terrestrial (mol N eq), freshwater (kg P equivalent) and marine (kg N equivalent)

Nutrients (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus) from sewage outfalls and fertilised farmland accelerate the growth of algae and other vegetation in water. The degradation of organic material consumes oxygen resulting in oxygen deficiency and, in some cases, fish death. Eutrophication translates the quantity of substances emitted into a common measure expressed as the oxygen required for the degradation of dead biomass.

To assess the impacts due to eutrophication, three EF impact categories are used: eutrophication, terrestrial; eutrophication, freshwater; eutrophication, marine.

Ecotoxicity (CTUe)

Environmental footprint impact category that addresses the toxic impacts on an ecosystem, which damage individual species and change the structure and function of the ecosystem. Ecotoxicity is a result of a variety of different toxicological mechanisms caused by the release of substances with a direct effect on the health of the ecosystem.

Land use (pt)

EF impact category related to use (occupation) and conversion (transformation) of land area by activities such as agriculture, roads, housing, mining, etc. Land occupation considers the effects of the land use, the amount of area involved and the duration of its occupation (changes in quality multiplied by area and duration). Land transformation considers the extent of changes in land properties and the area affected (changes in quality multiplied by the area).

Water use (m³ world equivalent)

No definition provided in reference European Commission (2013)

Impact category that addresses use of water.

Resource use, minerals and metals (kg Sb equivalent)

EF impact category that addresses use of natural resources, either renewable or non-renewable, biotic or abiotic.

Resource use, fossils (MJ)

EF impact category that addresses use of natural resources, either renewable or non-renewable, biotic or abiotic.

5.3 Annex C: List of critical raw materials

Source: Grohol M. and Veeh C., 2023

Critical raw Materials are indicated in bold while strategic raw materials are indicated in italics.

Material	Supply Risk (SR)	Economic Importance (EI)
Criticality threshold	1,0	2,8
Aggregates	0,2	3,2
Aluminium/bauxite	1,2	5,8
Antimony	1,8	5,4
Arsenic	1,9	2,9
Baryte	1,3	3,5
Bentonite	0,4	3,1
Beryllium	1,8	5,4
<i>Bismuth</i>	1,9	5,7
<i>Boron</i>	3,6	3,9
Cadmium	0,2	4,1
Chromium	0,7	7,2
Cobalt	2,8	6,8
Coking coal	1	3,1
<i>Copper</i>	0,1	4
Diatomite	0,3	2,3
Feldspar	1,5	3,2
Fluorspar	1,1	3,8
<i>Gallium</i>	3,9	3,7
<i>Germanium</i>	1,8	3,6
Gold	0,4	2,4
Gypsum	0,6	2,7
Hafnium	1,5	4,3
Helium	1,2	2,9
HREE	5,1	4,2
<i>HREE Dysprosium</i>	5,6	7,8
HREE Erbium	5,6	3,5
HREE Europium	5,6	3,3
<i>HREE Gadolinium</i>	3,3	3,3
HREE Holmium	5,6	3,2
HREE Lutetium	5,6	5
<i>HREE Terbium</i>	4,9	6,4
HREE Thulium	5,6	3,2
HREE Ytterbium	5,6	3,2
HREE Yttrium	3,5	2,9
Hydrogen	0,5	2,9
Indium	0,6	2,6
Iron ore	0,5	7,2
Kaolin clay	0,8	2,8
Krypton	0,7	3,3
Lead	0,1	4,2
Limestone	0,3	3,6
Lithium	1,9	3,9
LREE	3,7	5,9

LREE Cerium	4	4,9
LREE Lanthanum	3,5	2,9
LREE Neodymium	4,5	7,2
Praseodymium	3,2	7
LREE Samarium	3,5	7,7
Magnesite	0,6	3,6
Magnesium	4,1	7,4
Manganese	1,2	6,9
Molybdenum	0,8	6,7
Natural cork	0,9	1,7
Natural graphite	1,8	3,4
Natural Rubber	0,9	6
Natural Teak wood	1,7	2,4
Neon	0,7	3,1
<i>Nickel</i>	0,5	5,7
Niobium	4,4	6,5
Perlite	0,8	2,5
PGM	2,7	7,1
PGM Iridium	3,9	6,4
PGM Palladium	1,5	8,1
PGM Rhodium	2,4	8,6
PGM Ruthenium	3,8	5,5
Phosphate rock	1	6,4
Phosphorus	3,3	4,7
Potash	0,7	6,2
Rhenium	0,5	2,3
Roundwood	0,1	1,2
Sapele wood	1,3	1,6
Scandium	2,4	3,7
Selenium	0,3	4,8
Silica sand	0,3	3,1
Silicon metal	1,3	4,9
Silver	0,8	4,6
Strontium	2,6	6,5
Sulphur	0,3	5
Talc	0,2	3,3
Tantalum	1,3	4,8
Tellurium	0,3	3,8
Tin	0,9	4,5
Titanium	0,5	5,4
Titanium metal	1,6	6,3
Tungsten	1,2	8,7
Vanadium	2,3	3,9
Xenon	0,8	3,1
Zinc	0,2	4,8
Zirconium	0,8	3,5

5.4 Annex D: Eco-design requirements according to the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)

Durability & reliability

- (a) Durability and reliability of the product or its components as expressed through the product's guaranteed lifetime, technical lifetime, mean time between failures, indication of real use information on the product, resistance to stresses or ageing mechanisms;
- (s) functional performance and conditions for use, including as expressed through the ability to perform its intended use, precautions for use, skills required and compatibility with other products or systems;

Upgradability, reusability and the possibility of refurbishment and remanufacturing

- (c) Ease of upgrading, reuse, remanufacturing and refurbishment as expressed through number of materials and components used, use of standard components, use of component and material coding standards for the identification of components and materials, number and complexity of processes and tools needed, ease of non-destructive disassembly and re-assembly, conditions for access to product data, conditions for access to or use of hardware and software needed, conditions of access to test protocols or not commonly available testing equipment, availability of guarantees specific to remanufactured or refurbished products, conditions for access to or use of technologies protected by intellectual property rights, modularity.
- (e) Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to repair and maintenance of products and components.

Repairability and the possibility of maintenance

- (b) Ease of repair and maintenance, as expressed through characteristics, availability, delivery time and affordability of spare parts, modularity, compatibility with commonly available tools and spare parts, availability of repair and maintenance instructions, number of materials and components used, use of standard components, use of component and material coding standards for the identification of components and materials, number and complexity of processes and whether specialised tools are needed, ease of non-destructive disassembly and re-assembly, conditions for access to product data, conditions for access to or use of hardware and software needed.
- (l) Quantity, characteristics and availability of consumables needed for proper use and maintenance as expressed, inter alia, through yield, technical lifetime, ability to reuse, repair, and remanufacture, mass-resource efficiency, and interoperability;
- (e) Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to repair and maintenance of products and components.

Recyclability

- (d) Design for recycling, ease and quality of recycling as expressed through use of easily recyclable materials, safe, easy and non-destructive access to recyclable components and materials or components and materials containing hazardous substances and material composition and homogeneity, possibility for high-purity sorting, number of materials and components used, use of standard components, use of component and material coding standards for the identification of components and materials, number and complexity of processes and tools needed, ease of non-destructive disassembly and re-assembly, conditions for access to product data, conditions for access to or use of hardware and software needed.
- (e) Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental to recycling of products and components.

The presence of substances of concern

- (f) Use of substances, and in particular the use of substances of concern, on their own, as constituents of substances or in mixtures, during the production process of products, or leading to their presence in products, including once those products become waste, and their impacts on human health and the environment;

Energy use and energy efficiency, water use and water efficiency, resource use and resource efficiency

- (g) Use or consumption of energy, water and other resources in one or more life cycle stages of the product, including the effect of physical factors or software and firmware updates on product efficiency and including the impact on deforestation;
- (j) Weight and volume of the product and its packaging, and the product-to-packaging ratio;
- (t) Lightweight design as expressed through reduction of material consumption, load- and stress-optimisation of structures, integration of functions within the material or into a single product component, use of lower density or high-strength materials and hybrid materials, with regard to material savings, recycling and other circularity aspects, and waste reduction.
- (i) Use or content of sustainable renewable materials;

Recycled (and reused) content & material recovery

- (h) Use or content of recycled materials and recovery of materials, including critical raw materials
- (k) Incorporation of used components;

Environmental impacts, including carbon footprint and environmental footprint

- (m) The environmental footprint of the product, expressed as a quantification, in accordance with the applicable delegated act, of a product's life cycle environmental impacts, whether in relation to one or more environmental impact categories or an aggregated set of impact categories;
- (n) The carbon footprint of the product;
- (o) The material footprint of the product;
- (p) Microplastic and nanoplastic release as expressed through the release during relevant product life cycle stages, including manufacturing, transport, use and end-of-life stages;
- (q) Emissions to air, water or soil released in one or more lifecycle stages of the product as expressed through quantities and nature of emissions, including noise;

Expected generation of waste

- (r) Amounts of waste generated, including plastic waste and packaging waste and their ease of reuse, and amounts of hazardous waste generated;